

**“MUDRA loan & its Impact on Micro, Small and Medium
Enterprises Beneficiaries in Karnataka”**

A Report

Submitted in Partial Fulfilment of the Requirements for Award

of

POST DOCTORAL FELLOW

by

Dr. MAHESH K M

Roll No: 21SUPDR008

Under the supervision of

Dr. P. S. Aithal

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Declaration

I hereby declare that except where specific reference is made to the work of others, the contents of this Report is original and have not been submitted in whole or in part for consideration for any other degree or qualification in this, or any other University. This report is my own work and does not contain any outcome of work done in collaboration with others, except as specified in the text and Acknowledgements.

Signature:

Name : Dr. Mahesh K.M

Roll No : 21SUPDR008

Place : Mangalore

Date :

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Srinivas Nagar,-574 146, Mangalore, Phone :0824-77456

(Private University Established by Karnataka Govt. ACT No.42 of 2013.

Web:www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in Email: info@srinivasunivesity.edu.in

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Dr. Mahesh. K. M.

MUDRA loan and its impact on Micro, Small and Medium Enterprise Beneficiaries in Karnataka

SYNOPSIS

Submitted by

Dr MAHESH K M

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

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Introduction

In India, Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) play an important role in sustainable economic development. MSME sector has emerged as a vivacious sector of the Indian economy over many years now. MSMEs play a pivotal role in providing employment opportunities at comparatively lower capital costs than any large industry in India. MSMEs help in the industrialization and digitization of rural & backward areas and hence it reduces regional imbalances. It also assures more equitable distribution of national income and wealth. MSMEs harmonize large industries as ancillary units and they contribute enormously to the socio-economic development of the country as it is more popular among the informal sector in the manufacturing and service industry. Ministry of Micro, Small & Medium Enterprises (MSME) has envisioned a vibrant MSME sector by promoting growth and development of the Sector. This includes Khadi, Village and Coir Industries, in cooperation with concerned Ministries/Departments, State Governments and other Stakeholders. They also provide support to existing enterprises and encourages creation of new enterprises. In India, the enterprises form of organizations has been classified into (i) Manufacturing; and (ii) Services.

The MSME sector has performed exceptionally good and has enabled our country to achieve Industrial growth. A wide measure of industrial growth and diversification has been possible only with MSME sector in India. The major advantage being, less capital intensive and high labour absorption rate. This sector has made noteworthy contributions to employment generation through rural industrialization and is ideally suited to build on the strengths of our traditional culture, ancient skills and knowledge. These traditional insights have been infused with technologies, capital and innovative marketing practices.

It is for the less capital-intensive nature of that MSMEs, the government of India has introduced MUDRA, that is **Micro Unit Development and Refinance Agency Ltd**, loan with a main aim to

fund the unfunded. MUDRA is providing support to non-farming enterprises and it also adds to the welfare of individuals to engage in small-scale business which acts as a backbone of the Indian economy as nearly 40% of the revenues from the Industries in the Indian economy is from the small-scale sector. MUDRA will help in boosting the moral of the young entrepreneurs and fulfil the monetary needs (Bansal et.al, 2019) and has the potential to be a game changer, aims to provide financial support to Micro, Small and Medium entrepreneurs. They also aim at meeting their credit requirements by offering an opportunity to grow and expand business.

MUDRA (Micro Unit Development and Refinance Agency Ltd.)

MUDRA scheme was launched by Hon'ble Prime Minister, Shri. Narendra Modi ji, on April 8, 2015 for providing loan up to Rs.10 lakhs to the non-corporate and non-farm small & micro enterprises. This scheme was launched with the objective of providing the micro units, an opportunity to conduct business and encourage entrepreneurship in India. MUDRA would benefit fruit and vegetable sellers, food service units, machine operators, truck and taxi operators, hair salons, repair shops, artisans etc. in a rural and urban area with financing requirements depending upon the business of the entrepreneur. The MUDRA loans are extended under following three categories:

- Loans up to Rs. 50,000, the scheme is named Shishu
- Loans from Rs.50,001 to Rs.5 lakh, the scheme is named Kishore
- Loans from Rs. 5,00,001/- to Rs.10 lakh, the scheme is named Tarun

The scheme “Shishu” needs more focus as the loan amount is very meagre. Under this scheme more preference will be given to Shishu category and then Kishore and Tarun category units. Different segments of the industry have been catered to, in the process of MUDRA loan designs under the

Shishu, Kishore and Tarun category. There are other schemes that were launched as sector/activity specific schemes like business activities in Land Transport, Community, Social and Personal services and Food and Textile product sectors.

MUDRA for MSMEs

The MSME sector has hailed the establishment of Micro Units Development Refinance Agency (MUDRA) Bank with a provision of Rs.20,000 crore for micro and small-scale units. It has also granted Rs.3,000 crore for sanctioning loans to the MSME sector without collateral/guarantee security or third-party guarantee with a limit of Rs.1 crore (George et al., 2018). MUDRA is designed to fund and support Micro Finance Institutions (MFIs), which would in turn offer loans to a small bunch of businesses, which will have a preliminary corpus/capital of Rs.20,000 crore and a credit guarantee corpus of Rs.3,000 crore. Micro/Small businesses can avail of loans up to Rs.50,000; businesses that are a little bigger could avail of loans up to Rs.5 lakh; the highest range of loans available to the MSMEs is Rs.10 lakhs. To further finance, the MSME sector-affiliated entrepreneurs/businessmen would be given a “MUDRA card” and a credit of up to Rs.20,000 can be availed as extra credit. MUDRA Yojana, thus, will provide much-needed financial and institutional access to MSMEs, thereby promoting the growth of small businesses and helping boost the country’s GDP by creating jobs and options for self-employment.

Government Initiatives and Developments

The Government has initiated a unique One-Stop Digital Portal Linking Government Schemes. It is called “JanSamarth Portal”. It is an initiative by the Government of India and is a unique digital portal linking thirteen credit-linked Government Schemes on a single platform, for ease of access to all the beneficiaries and related stakeholders. The core objective of the JanSmarth portal is to provide inclusive growth and development of various sectors by guiding and providing them with the right type of Government benefits through a simple and easy digital process. The portal ensures end-to-end coverage of all the processes and activities of all the linked schemes.

The portal uses cutting-edge technologies and smart analytics to provide intuitive guidance to beneficiaries for checking subsidy eligibility and the auto recommendation system offers the best suitable schemes as per the beneficiary’s requirements and credentials. Advanced technologies automate entire lending processes based on digital verifications making the entire process simple, speedy and hassle-free.

This portal was unveiled on June 6, 2022, to make sure loan obtainment is hassle-free for the citizens. This avoids the user to visit separate websites for each scheme. The portal will check the eligibility, give in-principle sanctions and send the application to the selected bank. It will also keep the beneficiaries updated at each stage of the journey and help avoid multiple visits to bank branches.

Research Gaps

The extensive review of literature in this study has led to the detection of Research Gaps. There were gaps found in the literature concerning content gaps and methodological gaps. In terms of content, a lot of studies have depicted MUDRA loan studies but have not concentrated on the beneficiaries. The point of view of beneficiaries and their impact on them have not been studied particularly in the

literature. In terms of methodology, this study has conducted both qualitative and quantitative analysis and many of the studies have performed only the quantitative side of the analysis. Though the data is from a secondary source, it has been directly obtained from the Government's MUDRA loans department in Mumbai and has been the latest data. This is one of the factors that is missing in many research papers. Opinion-based analysis and interpretation have been emphasized in many of the studies.

Need of the study

MSMEs play an important role in the economic growth of our country. Funding, being the major challenge for the MSMEs, Government has introduced the MUDRA scheme for the needy. This scheme is primarily aimed at MSME units across the country. It was established with the sole purpose of funding and saving small entrepreneurs from abuse by money lenders and helping 1.5 crore new entrepreneurs in developing small businesses. They also provide and generate employment opportunities. They enhance financial literacy access for the New Technology and Non-Corporate Small Business Sectors (NCSBS) so as not to depend upon money lenders; rather they can approach the financial institutions and bring them under Mudra Borrower Scheme. The scheme also seeks to empower and emancipate women and fund the unfunded new entrepreneur. However, there is a huge lacuna in the system as identified in the literature and the initial surveys conducted while writing this proposal. The challenges are in the areas of awareness among the general public, practical processing problems by the banking professionals and identification of actual beneficiaries for the loans. With this background, there is an ardent need to understand the role of MUDRA in entrepreneurship and its impact on Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) beneficiaries. Therefore, the present study attempts to study the same.

Research Questions

The present study revolves around the following research questions:

1. Is the MUDRA scheme really benefiting the stakeholders?
2. Are MSMEs aware of MUDRA schemes and their details?
3. What is the impact of MUDRA schemes on the MSME beneficiaries?
4. Are the youth getting motivated to take up entrepreneurship through MUDRA schemes?

Any other relevant questions that might arise in the course of the study will also be considered.

Objectives of the Study:

The study has the following major objectives:

1. To evaluate the impact of the MUDRA scheme on Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) beneficiaries.
2. To create an impact by documenting the cases.

Scope of the Study:

- **Conceptual Scope:**

The present study is confined to the study of the role of MUDRA loans and their impact on the MSME beneficiaries. To have an unbiased view, the exploratory scope is considered and thereby leading to the study of the actual impact on the beneficiaries.

- **Geographical Scope:**

The present study has considered Karnataka as the geographical scope for two reasons-

According to the regional analysis depicted in MUDRA Annual Report 2019-2020, the South region has a clear mention of the performance concerning Target Vs Achievement on loan sanctions and disbursements. South region has the performance of 29% which is high compared to other regions as mentioned in the below chart.

Source: MUDRA Annual Report-2019-20

Out of the top 10 districts rated based on their performance, 50% of the top districts are covered in Southern India. Five districts – Hyderabad, Bangalore Urban, Tiruchirappalli, Belgaum and Chennai are among the top 10 districts as shown in the table below. Hence the present study considers Karnataka as the sample region for data collection.

Data collection

As a part of primary data collection, various questionnaires and survey instruments were designed as applicable to collect relevant data from various stakeholders. The secondary data includes information from online journals, books, reports and other documents pertaining to the study. Most importantly, MUDRA loans data was collected directly from the Government of India Directorate on MUDRA loans through email mode.

Qualitative data was also collected from the direct beneficiaries of the MUDRA loan and case study methodology has been applied to study and analyse the qualitative data. An initial attempt was made at the time of proposal writing to understand the nuances of MUDRA loans which included understanding the needs of the customers, banking professionals' view on MUDRA loan sanctions and disbursements and another view of the youth who are either existing entrepreneurs or potential entrepreneurs.

Preliminary Survey Results

As a part of background work to arrive at the objectives and research questions, a small qualitative survey was conducted among 30 respondents. The respondents were conveniently selected based on the study's requirements.

Fig 3.3: Respondents of the Preliminary Survey

Source: Original Preliminary Survey by the author (2021)

Three separate open-ended survey forms were used to collect qualitative data and were analysed.

- The first set of respondents were the existing Entrepreneurs in small businesses. They have posed a question about their views on the MUDRA scheme and many of them believed that more entrepreneurs should be educated about this scheme and that the Government should reach the public at large. A few of them also felt that this scheme has made them self-dependent and in turn, boosts the economy of the country.
- The second set of respondents was from the Banking Institutions whose Banking service experiences ranged from 5 to 31 years. Out of these respondents, few of them were of the opinion that the Government should stop all subsidy-related schemes and give the interest incentive so that the public money reaches the actual beneficiaries. Many of them felt that the process should be made simpler for sanctions and disbursements. Few of them have perceived that the identification of beneficiaries is the biggest challenge for the banks.
- The third set of respondents who were the youth was of the opinion that many of them were not aware of such a scheme which is existing in the Banks and is introduced by the Government of India. Few youths were of the view that assessment of the business proposals and strict vigilance of their business is necessary to make sure the money is utilised appropriately. Many youths have also urged that government should encourage aspiring young entrepreneurs by helping them with less paperwork and faster approval of loans.

Apart from the above excerpts, many suggestions and ideas were also presented by the respondents during the online discussion of the topic. Based on these thoughts, the objectives and the research study mapping have been designed.

Statistical Techniques for Data Analysis

The present study is aimed at the analysis of the data from both the qualitative and quantitative ends. Relevant analytical tools will be used in the course of the research.

Kishore Loans as a %

Tarun Loans as a %

List of Hypotheses:

I H_0 ; There is no significant difference between Shishu, Kishore or Tarun loans (as a percentage of total) sanctioned/disbursed by banks.

H_1 ; There is a significant difference between Shishu, Kishore or Tarun loans (as a percentage of total) sanctioned/disbursed by banks.

II H_0 ; There is no significant difference between Shishu, Kishore or Tarun loans (as a percentage of total) sanctioned/disbursed by financial institutions.

H_1 ; There is a significant difference between Shishu, Kishore or Tarun loans (as a percentage of total) sanctioned/disbursed by financial institutions.

III H_0 ; There is no significant difference between Shishu loans (as a percentage of total) sanctioned/disbursed by banks and financial institutions.

H_1 ; There is a significant difference between Shishu loans (as a percentage of total) sanctioned/disbursed by banks and financial institutions.

IV H₀; There is no significant difference between Kishore loans (as a percentage of total sanctioned/disbursed by banks and financial institutions.

H₁; There is a significant difference between Kishore loans (as a percentage of total sanctioned/disbursed by banks and financial institutions.

V H₀; There is no significant difference between Tarun loans (as a percentage of total sanctioned/disbursed by banks and financial institutions.

H₁; There is a significant difference between Tarun loans (as a percentage of total sanctioned/disbursed by banks and financial institutions.

Qualitative Analysis:

As a part of the qualitative analysis exercise, entrepreneurs who have availed of MUDRA loans were interviewed and the responses were analysed. The following word cloud was created out of the responses and the paragraphs that follow the cloud have the details of the qualitative factors arrived out of the analysis.

3.7.1 No Collateral Security: Since MUDRA loans do not expect any collateral security to be provided against the loans, it is easy to secure. Entrepreneurs were happy with this arrangement and felt relieved that not all the businessmen do not have collateral security to present.

3.7.2 More Employment: MUDRA loans have created employment for many people. When the businesses are expanded, entrepreneurs tend to hire employees to manage their businesses. The loan gives them support to hire people.

3.7.3 Easy Business Expansion: Business expansion is easy when a MUDRA loan is availed. The entrepreneurs are stress-free and can easily expand their business.

3.7.4 Increases Confidence: MUDRA loans provide easy access to loans and the businessmen in this case study are of the opinion that it increases their confidence while conducting business.

3.7.5 Increased Self-Employment: A lot of people get the strength and support to start businesses and become self-employed instead of waiting for getting employment elsewhere. It encourages the youth to take up self-employed businesses.

3.7.6 Financial Improvement: Due to MUDRA loans, the financial stability of the business will be improved. It boosts the financial status of the entrepreneurs to a considerable extent.

4.0 Social Impact of this Research

The Impact of this research reaches beyond academia, though academia will also be benefited from the results of this research. The teaching fraternity should go beyond the set boundaries and teach the students of management about entrepreneurship which is the best alternative for employment. Students at a young age should be made aware that their innovative ideas will not go waste due to a lack of financial availability. Even though they cannot get the finances to the extent they expect, the Government at present through their initiatives and JanSamarth portal is trying to assist and handhold new ideas. The dissemination of this work will also generate a significant impact and will help the bankers to use it as a reference.

5.0 Conclusion

The Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana (PMMY) has been continuously serving millions of unfunded micro-borrowers in our country with finances that are crucial for their businesses and enterprise activities which has resulted in the upliftment of their lifestyles. The PMMY programme, since its announcement, in the last five years, has benefited 24.48 crore loan accounts, with a loan sanction of

a whopping 18.6 trillion rupees, since the year 2015. This has enabled the grassroots of the economy of the country and contributed in a bigger way to the overall economic growth. The proposed study is about to contribute extensively to MSME stakeholders and academicians. Researchers in this area should also consider disseminating these kinds of cases to the general public and the academic arena and make sure it reaches many people and help them get greater benefits through various Government initiatives. The rural public should also be created awareness about the schemes and help them to grow through the MUDRA loan set-up.

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Chapter-1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction

In India, Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) play an important role in sustainable economic development. MSME sector has emerged as a vivacious sector of the Indian economy for many years now. MSMEs play a pivotal role in providing employment opportunities at comparatively lower capital costs than any large industry in India. MSMEs help in the industrialization and digitization of rural & backward areas and hence it reduces regional imbalances. It also assures a more equitable distribution of national income and wealth. MSMEs harmonize large industries as ancillary units and they contribute enormously to the socio-economic development of the country as it is more popular among the informal sector in the manufacturing and service industry. Ministry of Micro, Small & Medium Enterprises (MSME) has envisioned a vibrant MSME sector by promoting growth and development of the Sector. This includes Khadi, Village and Coir Industries, in cooperation with concerned Ministries/Departments, State Governments and other Stakeholders. They also provide support to existing enterprises and encourage the creation of new enterprises. In India, the enterprises form of organizations has been classified into (i) Manufacturing; and (ii) Services. The MSME sector has enormous opportunities due to the following characteristics, depicted in the chart below.

Less Capital Intensive

Extensive Promotion & Support by Government

Reservation for Exclusive small-scale sector

Machinery Procurement

Funding - Finance & Subsidies

Raw Material Procurement

Manpower Training

Technical & Managerial skills

Tooling & Testing support

Reservation for Exclusive Purchase by Government

Export Promotion

Growth in demand in the domestic market size due to overall economic growth

Increasing Export Potential for Indian products

Growth in Requirements for ancillary units due to the increase in the number of greenfield units coming up in the large-scale sector.

The MSME sector has performed exceptionally good and has enabled our country to achieve Industrial growth. A wide measure of industrial growth and diversification has been possible only with the MSME sector in India. The major advantages are less capital intensive and a high labour absorption rate. This sector has made noteworthy contributions to employment generation through rural industrialization and is ideally suited to build on the strengths of our traditional culture, ancient skills and knowledge. These traditional insights have been infused with technologies, capital and innovative marketing practices.

MSMEs in India has been considered a major contributor to economic growth. The Indian Government has tried many ways and means to make India, a self-employed entrepreneurs' economy. India has approximately 6.3 crores of MSMEs and to boost the sector, the Government has announced funds worth Rs. 10,000 crores for the Guarantee Emergency Credit Line (GECL) scheme facility to eligible MSMEs borrowers, in the year 2021. The MSME sector acts as a catalyst to bring about social and economic transformation. The Government has announced various relief measures under Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyaan. The SMEs are defined under MSMED Act 2006 as MSMEs and the Retail and wholesale trade enterprises were brought under the MSMEs Development Act 2006. To strengthen the MSMEs and to extend various government schemes & economic growth, the Minister of MSME included 2.5 crore retail and wholesale enterprises under the MSMEs.

It is for the less capital-intensive nature of that MSMEs, the government of India has introduced MUDRA, that is **Micro Unit Development and Refinance Agency Ltd**, the loan with the main aim to fund the unfunded. MUDRA is providing support to non-farming enterprises and it also adds to the welfare of individuals to engage in small-scale business which acts as a backbone of the Indian economy as nearly 40% of the revenues from the Industries in the Indian economy is from the small-scale sector. MUDRA will help in boosting the morale of the young entrepreneurs and fulfil their

monetary needs (Bansal et.al, 2019) and has the potential to be a game-changer, aims to provide financial support to Micro, Small and Medium entrepreneurs. They also aim at meeting their credit requirements by offering an opportunity to grow and expand their business.

MUDRA Loan is regarded as a vital tool for overall economic development in India (Gautam, 2020). Mudra Scheme is also one of the most important instruments for Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises in generating employment. It provides support by refinancing to banks, Microfinance Institutions (MFIs) and NBFC for providing loans to small units having a loan up to 10 lakhs. Under the MUDRA umbrella, loans are provided by Commercial Banks, Small Finance Banks, MFIs & NBFCs. A survey by NSSO in 2015-16 has revealed that Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) have created 11.10 crore jobs. The MSME Sector is an impacting aid to the Indian Economy which currently contributes to about 44% of the total national GDP which means, that around 45% of export and 67 million MSMEs are operating in the non-Agri sector in India. This is a combination of both unorganised and organised sectors together. Mudra loans are provided without any demand for any collateral security from the MSMEs.

Fig 1.1: MSMEs – An analysis

Source: India Brand Equity Foundation, 2021

A committee on Micro, Small and Medium enterprises set by the RBI has recommended and implemented a hike in loan sanctions under MUDRA from Rs.10 lakhs to Rs. 20 lakhs.

Fig 1.2: Number of Registered MSMEs in India

Source: India Brand Equity Foundation, 2021

The government has proposed many subsidies and incentives to promote entrepreneurs belonging to the women and special categories of entrepreneurs. Small Industries Development Bank of India (SIDBI), which is the principal financial institution focusing on Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in the country, has deployed a ‘project management unit’ (PMU) in 11 states. The states are Gujarat, Odisha, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu, New Delhi, Haryana, Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh, Uttarakhand, Andhra Pradesh & Karnataka to strengthen MSMEs in their respective states. The PMU will look at preparing a process for hand-holding local MSMEs for their placement onto digital platforms such as PSB Loans In 59 Minutes, stock exchange listing, e-commerce platforms such as Government e-marketplace (GeM) and facilitating awareness on activities and schemes for MSMEs by the state government under the Atmanirbhar Bharat programme. In India, 6.3 crore MSMEs contribute 29% of GDP and in Karnataka 7.85 lakh Registered MSMEs have an investment accounting for more than 83,000 crore and employing 54.31 lakh people. MSMEs are labour intensive and play a strategic role in commercializing new inventions and products (Mangurish Pai Raiker, 2017).

Table-1.1: Employment provided by MSMEs (No. in Lakhs)

Sector	Micro	Small	Medium	Total	Share (%)
Rural	489.30	7.88	0.60	497.78	45
Urban	586.88	24.06	1.16	612.10	55
All	1076.	31.95	1.75	1109.89	100

Source: MSMEs Annual Report 2020-21

1.2 MUDRA (Micro Unit Development and Refinance Agency Ltd.)

MUDRA scheme was launched by Hon’ble Prime Minister, Shri. Narendra Modi Ji, on April 8, 2015, for providing loans up to Rs.10 lakhs to the non-corporate and non-farm small & micro-enterprises. This scheme was launched to provide the micro-units, an opportunity to conduct business and encourage entrepreneurship in India. MUDRA would benefit fruit and vegetable sellers, food service units, machine operators, truck and taxi operators, hair salons, repair shops, artisans etc. in a rural and urban areas with financing requirements depending upon the business of the entrepreneur. The MUDRA loans are extended under the following three categories:

- Loans up to Rs. 50,000, the scheme is named Shishu
- For loans from Rs.50,001 to Rs.5 lakh, the scheme is named Kishore
- Loans from Rs. 5,00,001/- to Rs.10 lakh, the scheme is named Tarun

The scheme “Shishu” needs more focus as the loan amount is very meagre. Under this scheme, more preference will be given to the Shishu category and then Kishore and Tarun category units. Different segments of the industry have been catered to, in the process of MUDRA loan designs under the

Shishu, Kishore and Tarun categories. Other schemes were launched as sector/activity specific schemes like business activities in Land Transport, Community, Social and Personal services and Food and Textile product sectors. The schemes are discussed briefly in the following paragraphs:

Micro Credit Scheme (MCS): The Government has extended financial support to MFIs for lending to individuals/groups of individuals and sometimes to the self-help groups. This is for the creation of qualifying assets as per RBI guidelines towards setting the micro-enterprises as per MSMED Act.

Refinance Scheme for Regional Rural Banks (RRBs) and Scheduled Co-operative Banks: This scheme is available for both manufacturing and service sector enterprises. It enhances the liquidity of RRBs or scheduled Cooperative banks by refinancing loans extended to micro enterprises as per MSME Act, with beneficiary loan sizes up to Rs.10 lakh per enterprise/borrower.

Mahila Uddyami Scheme: Under this scheme, women entrepreneurs are encouraged. This scheme is set up to provide timely and sufficient financial support to the MFIs, for lending to women or self-help groups for the creation of qualifying assets.

Business Loan for Traders & Shopkeepers: This scheme helps in timely and adequate financial support to individuals for running shops and small enterprises. It also caters to trading and business activities, service and non-farm income-generating activities with a beneficiary loan size of up to Rs.10 lakh per enterprise or borrower.

Missing Middle Credit Scheme: This scheme is beneficial for financial intermediaries. The financial intermediaries can take this support for lending to individuals or enterprises to set up new businesses. The funds can also be used for the expansion of existing businesses as per the MSMED Act. As per this act, non- farm income-generating activities can be funded with a beneficiary loan limit of Rs. 50,000 to Rs.10 lakh per enterprise /borrower.

The Mudra loan scheme has been designed by the Government of India to promote entrepreneurship among the current generation. The objective was to promote and provide financial assistance to micro and small businesses via financial institutions like banks and NBFCs. It is one of the finest financial options for entrepreneurs and small businesses majorly involved in Self-employment. This allows the entrepreneurs to use the loans for a wide variety of purposes. Mudra loans provide the much-needed funds for vendors, traders, shopkeepers and other service sector entrepreneurs. It helps the businessmen to utilise the funds for working capital loans, equipment finance, vehicle loans (for commercial use), etc.

It is important to understand that the Mudra scheme does not directly provide financial support to the micro and small enterprises but offers to refinance support to Nationalised and Commercial banks, Regional Rural Banks (RRBs), and small-finance banks and NBFCs. Furthermore, Mudra loans can be availed only by those businesses that come under non-farm activities like generation, manufacturing, artisan, trading or service industries. It is a collateral-free loan which can be used for a wide range of business expenses. In Tamil Nadu, from the total number of loans provided under the MUDRA scheme, most of the percentage that is 70% of borrowers are women. The government data on MUDRA loans indicate that the percentage of women who are joining micro-enterprises and NCSBS is mounting. However, many studies opine that there is a need for a mechanism to check whether the amount of loans availed by the women are being used by them or are these going to the male members of the family, who are running the business in the name of women in the household.

Fig 1.3: MUDRA loans - Top 3 States' Performance

Source: MUDRA Annual Report 2019-20

1.3 MUDRA for MSMEs

The MSME sector has hailed the establishment of Micro Units Development Refinance Agency (MUDRA) Bank with a provision of Rs.20,000 crore for micro and small-scale units. It has also granted Rs.3,000 crore for sanctioning loans to the MSME sector without collateral/guarantee security or third-party guarantee with a limit of Rs.1 crore (George et al., 2018). MUDRA is designed to fund and support Micro Finance Institutions (MFIs), which would in turn offer loans to a small bunch of businesses, which will have a preliminary corpus/capital of Rs.20,000 crore and a credit guarantee corpus of Rs.3,000 crore. Micro/Small businesses can avail of loans up to Rs.50,000; businesses that are a little bigger could avail of loans up to Rs.5 lakh; the highest range of loans available to the MSMEs is Rs.10 lakhs. To further finance, the MSME sector-affiliated entrepreneurs/businessmen would be given a “MUDRA card” and a credit of up to Rs.20,000 can be availed as extra credit. MUDRA Yojana, thus, will provide much-needed financial and institutional access to MSMEs, thereby promoting the growth of small businesses and helping boost the country’s GDP by creating jobs and options for self-employment.

Table 1.2: Agency-wise performance

Category	Target (2019-20) Rs in Crore	Sanction (2019-20) Rs in Crore	Sanction (2018-19) Rs in Crore	Growth (%)
Public Sector Banks (incl. Regional Rural Banks)	1,28,000	1, 17,729 (92%)	1,17,282	7
Private Sector Banks (incl. Foreign Banks)	70,025	91,780 (132%)	64,037	43
Small Finance Banks	29,350	29,501 (101%)	29,794	-1
Micro Finance Institutions	57,425	57,967 (101%)	63,471	-9
Non-Banking Finance Companies	40,200	40,518 (101%)	47,137	-14
Total	3,25,000	3, 37,495 (104%)	3,21,721	5

Source: MUDRA Annual Report-2019-20

The funding and finance through banks are one major component of the promotion of entrepreneurship in MSMEs for the Social – Economic development of the country. The MSMEs enterprises are Furniture manufacturing, Hotels and Restaurants, Retail trade, manufacturing of food and beverage and manufacturing of wearing apparel and many more and the beneficiaries are women. New entrepreneur and special category of borrowers – SC, ST, OBC.

Table 1.3: Mudra Loan Beneficiaries of Shishu, Kishor and Tarun Schemes

Category	No of Accounts	Amount Sanctioned	Amount Disbursed
Women	3,91,03,349 (63%)	1,45,182 (43%)	1,42,846 (43%)
New entrepreneur Accounts	1,19,13,903 (19%)	99,263 (29%)	94,896 (29%)
SC/ST/OBC	2,97,50,100 (48%)	1,13,884 (34%)	1,12,029 (34%)

Source: MUDRA Annual Report-2019-20

1.4: Loan Losses:

Public Sector Banks that offer MUDRA loans have witnessed a severe swell in the amount of MUDRA loans whirling into non-performing assets (NPAs). This has been the trend over the last three years. As per the Finance Ministry in the Government of India portal, NPAs in MUDRA loans have crossed Rs.18,835 crore in 2019-20, from Rs.11,483 crore in 2018-2019 and Rs.7,277 in 2017-18.

MUDRA disbursements/sanctions by state-owned banks have augmented to Rs.3.82 lakh crore in 2019-20, from Rs.3.05 lakh crore in 2018-19 and Rs.2.12 lakh crore in 2017-18. The MUDRA, NPAs as a percentage of total loans have risen to 4.92% in 2019-20 from 3.42 % in 2017-18.

The GOI has sanctioned loan amounts of Rs.15.5 lakh crore under PMMY since its inception in April 2015. Until March 31, 2021, the GOI had sanctioned 29.55 crore loans under this scheme. Out of more than 6.8 crores, loans worth Rs.5.2 lakh crores have been disbursed to new entrepreneurs/businesses. For FY 22, loans worth Rs.3,804 crore have been sanctioned by 13 Public Sector Banks/ Nationalised Banks as of June 25.

The growth of MSMEs has contributed to the increase in the ‘Make in India’ proposal. The small manufacturing units and self-employed individuals, not only in urban areas but also in rural areas are hugely getting benefitted from schemes like MUDRA. PMMY will concur with the financial well-being of the entrepreneurs involved in small-scale industries. While positively influencing the progress of the economy, MUDRA creates a vision of ratifying the informal sector thereby funding the unfunded. The USP of this scheme is that it has the role of an apex refiner and provides low-cost finance. In India’s microfinance arena, MUDRA has filled the huge gap and the measures of the Government in terms of MUDRA loans have immensely boosted the confidence of our young, educated and skilled workers. These young entrepreneurs who own the first-generation enterprises will be motivated in expanding their existing small businesses.

1.5 Government Initiatives and Developments

The Government has initiated a unique One-Stop Digital Portal Linking Government Schemes. It is called “JanSamarth Portal”. It is an initiative by the Government of India and is a unique digital portal linking thirteen credit-linked Government Schemes on a single platform, for ease of access to all the beneficiaries and related stakeholders. The core objective of the JanSmarth portal is to provide inclusive growth and development of various sectors by guiding and providing them with the right type of Government benefits through a simple and easy digital process. The portal ensures end-to-end coverage of all the processes and activities of all the linked schemes.

The portal uses cutting-edge technologies and smart analytics to provide intuitive guidance to beneficiaries for checking subsidy eligibility and the auto recommendation system offers the best suitable schemes as per the beneficiary’s requirements and credentials. Advanced technologies automate entire lending processes based on digital verifications making the entire process simple, speedy and hassle-free.

This portal was unveiled on June 6, 2022, to make sure loan obtainment is hassle-free for the citizens. This avoids the user to visit separate websites for each scheme. The portal will check the eligibility, give in-principle sanctions and send the application to the selected bank. It will also keep the beneficiaries updated at each stage of the journey and help avoid multiple visits to bank branches.

1.6 Summary:

In India, Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) play an important role in sustainable economic development. MSME sector has emerged as a vivacious sector of the Indian economy over many years now. In this chapter, a discussion has been made on how MUDRA loans have contributed to the growth of small MSMEs and expansion of existing MSMEs. It has also depicted various statistics on MUDRA loans and MSMEs supporting the title of the research.

Chapter 2

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1 Introduction

The present study has considered MUDRA loan studies for review in different states of India. There has been an intensive search for the literature in terms of the perspectives of the MSMEs. However, there have been studies which are based on other than MSMEs but are related to MUDRA loans. Also, there have been limitless studies conducted on various dimensions of the MSMEs and MUDRA loans in the research sphere and varied literature has been reviewed and presented in the following paragraphs, covering many dimensions.

2.2 Literature Reviews

In the Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business, the authors **Ajay Kumar Salgotra, Prashant Kandar and Uma Bahuguna (2021)** have researched and published an article titled “*Does Access to Finance Eradicate Poverty? A Case Study of Mudra Beneficiaries*”. They have conducted paired t-tests to test the impact and impression of access to finance across various magnitudes of poverty by structuring the Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI). This MPI has pondered over and provided us with dimensions such as education, health, and standard of living. The findings of the research have uncovered that various attributes of poverty have retorted positively to access to finance. The study shows that larger access to finance has helped in the reduction of multidimensional poverty by having a modest, but positive influence on the standard of living, health, and education. They have also opined that this has improved the lives of many people, both urban and rural. The current article reviewed has identified that the level of impact/ influence of access to finance is moderate and further explains its significance for policy implications.

Yogesh Mahajan (2021), In his paper titled “Financing Micro and Small Enterprises: Assessing the impact of Mudra Loans in an Emerging Economy”, focuses on the impact of MUDRA on small and micro-enterprises. This paper views the impact in terms of “income generation”, “standard of living”, “business expansion” and “employment generation” in the process. The author has presented the socio-economic research results by applying of mean difference method for quantitative data analysis. Relative importance index method has been adopted for qualitative data analysis. Through this research, it was found that though the enterprises benefited because of “collateral-free” MUDRA loans in terms of income generation and business expansion, the scheme did not have any significant impact on employment generation and standard of living. It was also observed during the survey that there was no scope for improvements in food and nutrition quality. On the other hand, the women entrepreneurs are not benefited from financial independence as found through the study by the author.

Sachin S Hiremath and Narayan S Ghanti (2021), in their research study titled “A Study of Effectiveness of Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana in Belagavi City” published in the International Research Journal of Humanities and Interdisciplinary Studies, have focused on the effectiveness of PMMY schemes and services, the behaviour of beneficiaries about MUDRA loans and the problems faced by the people in getting the MUDRA loan. The other objectives of this study are to analyze the business position of beneficiaries in the PMMY scheme and to get the awareness of people concerning various streams of the PMMY along with the employability position of the scheme beneficiaries. As observed by the authors, the MUDRA scheme has been fruitful in offering loans and financial assistance to the MSME with 91% of loans being disbursed below Rs. 50,000 in the Shishu scheme. The authors have also in this study have attempted to explore the bank's financial performance, reducing the unemployment rate and disbursed amount by the PMMY.

Mr Akbar Siddiqui Shaji Ahmed (2021), in his Research Article “A Study of Performance Evaluation of Pradhan Mantri Yojana (PMMY) with special reference to the Marathwada Region” intends to explore the status of Mudra loans in the State of Marathwada have attempted analysing as well as measuring the extent of the impact on various categories such as SC, ST, OBC, Women micro-enterprises in terms of loans sanctions. The author has also focused on the disparities in offering MUDRA loans to Micro and Small Enterprises. For this purpose, the author has collected both qualitative and quantitative data. Through this study, the author has found that there has been a constant increase in the sanction of loans to micro-enterprises in India with the majority of the category being the Shishu Category. Author suggests widening the development and increasing the loan sanction facility to Kishore and Tarun category also. And he also suggests increasing the loan amount to open economically backward category people.

P Arivalagan and Dr T Balasaravanan (2021), in their research study on “Analysis of Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana (PMMY) in Indian Economy”, have focused on the development of the Micro units and they are refinancing, vision, mission and purpose of Mudra, SWOT analysis of PMMY, benefits of Mudra Loan, credit support facility to the weaker sections and growth of disbursement of Mudra loans as well as its impact on the economy. On the other hand, through this study, the authors have observed that many financial institutions find it difficult to evaluate the credit worthiness of MSME customers because of a lack of history of their credit as they would not have maintained proper business records and hence not eligible for collateral security against the loan.

Subhro Sen Gupta and Dr Ranjul Rastogi (2021), have published their Research Article titled “A Descriptive Study of the Role of MUDRA Funding-Shishu over the Different States’ in EFFLATOUNARIA - Multidisciplinary Journal. The author’s main focus of this research study is

to examine and analyze the number of MUDRA accounts opened in the various years and also the average amount received under all the categories viz., SHISHU, TARUN and KISHORE.

Dr Singh Rupesh Roshan and Bindal Anita (2021), in their Research Article titled “Performance of Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana (PMMY) in Haryana State”, have focused mainly on the development of PMMY and the products offered by them concerning the industries located in Haryana State. As observed by the authors, the PMMY scheme is the most prominent scheme which offers the promotion of Financial inclusion in India where the entrepreneurs can take loans up to Rs. 10 lakhs to set up their business.

Talima Mukherjee (2021), to conduct a comparative analysis on whether there is any growth rate seen in accessing loans under the three categories of the same viz, Shishu, Kishore and Tarun between the period 2015 and 2020 by various sections of the society like General Category, Scheduled Caste, Scheduled Tribe and Other Backward Caste with respect to the number of accounts opened, loans sanctions & disbursed, Amount of loan sanctioned and disbursed per account opened on an average has published her Research Article titled “A Comparative Analysis on the Performance of Mudra Yojana from 2015-2020: with special reference to different sections of the society”. On the other hand, the Author’s secondary objective of this study is to how far this scheme/Yojana has been utilized by Women Entrepreneurs, Minorities and New entrepreneurs. With the detailed analysis and comparison, the author concludes that among the backward castes, only scheduled tribes are lagging in availing of the loans and on the other hand the percentage of borrowing Shishu Loan by women entrepreneurs has reached 65%. whereas there have been only 11 to 12% of minorities who have borrowed loans under this scheme as compared to Women entrepreneurs. Through this study, the author opines that the Government needs to analyze the reason for failure in the participation of Scheduled castes, Scheduled Tribes as well as Minorities in availing the loans and also since there

has been more scope for availing of a loan towards Shishu loan under Mudra scheme the limit of borrowing Rs. 50,000 must be enhanced for the betterment of the business.

Dr Satya R. Doley (2021), has published in Research Article titled “An Empirical Study on Assessment of Mudra Yojana in India” intending to assess the scheme-wise loan disbursed to the various account and also investigate the category-wise loan disbursed to different borrowing during the study period. The Research Study period considered by the author is from 2015-16 to 2019-20 and the secondary sources of data were also collected between these periods and analysed by using statistical tools like mean, standard deviation, skewness, kurtosis and ANOVA. As per the data analysed with the help of the statistical tools, the author opines that there has been a high mean and also the highest standard deviation with respect to loan disbursement of Shishu Account scheme. When the analysis was carried out with respect to a year than the year 2019-20 had the highest mean value with respect to the loan disbursement. On the other hand, the author also observed that when it comes to category-wise loan disbursement, the women entrepreneurs had the highest mean and standard deviation. According to the analysis and observation of the author, it is further found in the study that there has been a significant difference in scheme-wise loans disbursed to the account and on the other hand non-significant difference of year-wise loans disbursed to this account.

Amit Basak (2020), with an objective of evaluating the financial inclusion of Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana (PMMY), its progress as well as its impact on SMMEs has published a Research article titled “Mudra Initiatives for funding to MSME: A Big step for pushing Financial inclusion in India”. For the purpose of the research study the author has collected secondary data like journals, articles, research papers and reports of MUDRA from the official website. These data were analysed by using statistical tools like ratios and percentages. As observed due to the Pandemic Covid - 19 there has been a lot of shutdowns of the production units and MSME are struggling to clear their salary bills.

On the other hand the prolonged lockdown because of corona also throws a good opportunity to the businessmen to create it as a challenge to prosper in the business market. The author suggests growing the MSME by creating the concept 'Make in India' and manufacturing their own product which creates employment and also there is upliftment of the society along with the economy betterment. At this point of time the MUDRA loan helps the small manufacturing units in fulfilling their business dreams and also improve rural and urban areas. The aim of the PMMY scheme is to take the nation forward and make it a sustainable developed country. Mudra Banks also provides loans to the young population to grow as an entrepreneur. Hence the author suggests the entrepreneurs to focus on the slogan "Produce Local, Buy Local and Think Global".

Vijaykumar (2020), in an article titled "A comprehensive analysis of "Pradhan Mantri MUDRA Yojana" – Achievements and bottlenecks", from Institute of Business Management, GLA University, Mathura, has attempted to analyse the present trend of implementation of the scheme. This paper also analyses the disbursement trend by referring to the government reports as well as scholarly and journalistic work in this field. The paper may provide a ready reference to scholars/academicians interested in the field of financial inclusion, micro-finance and government policies.

Hareesh Kumar U R and Akhil Padmarajan (2020), in their Research Article titled "A study on the role of Micro Units Development and Refinancing Agency (MUDRA) Bank with special reference to Kerala" have made an attempt in examining the overall performance of MSME sector in Kerala and also to recognize the performance of MUDRA bank credit schemes in Kerala. The authors have conducted secondary data analysis to collect the information required for the study and have opined that the MSME units in the service sector. The authors through their study have also observed that the MUDRA scheme cannot completely fill the credit requirements of Micro unit entrepreneurs alone.

Reshma Raj, Shilpa H.S & KG Rajani (2019) ‘Problems Faced by Small Business entrepreneurs in obtaining credit Facilities from commercial Banks with Specific Reference to Mudra Loan’ mainly focused on the entrepreneurs in Kerala. The major problems faced by entrepreneurs in accessing the credit under the MUDRA loans were lengthy processing time for the loan application, the loans are collateral-free so a proper risk assessment of every disbursement would reduce the fear of banks in lending to small enterprises and it impacts the ultimate success of the scheme. The scheme will help to build young entrepreneurs in India.

V. Poornima (2019), has published her Research Article titled “A Study on Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana: Mudra Scheme” in International Journal of Advance Research in Computer Science and Management Studies. The main intention of this study is to perceive the PMMY scheme and its products and thereby analyse the performance of those products offered under the Refinance scheme. For this purpose the author has collected secondary data from various journals, articles, reports from websites of MSME and MUDRA. The data collected by the author was ranging from the period 2015-16 to 2018-19 Financial Year. Through this study the author opines that the MUDRA scheme is bringing a new hope for both existing and aspiring micro enterprises as well as women entrepreneurs. Hence there is a need for promoting such small and micro enterprises who contribute to the country’s economy and thereby an opportunity for employment, exports and GDP is created. Author also suggests loosening the procedural difficulties in the MUDRA scheme for the betterment of the MSME sector.

Binija George & J. Nalini (2018) In this article discusses “ Role of MUDRA Bank in the growth of MSMEs” Indian MSME sectors a reality by launching a dedicated bank for MSME sector is known as MUDRA bank will spur the growth of Indian MSME sector and help them to increase their contribution to Indian GDP and role played by MUDRA bank towards Micro, Small and Medium

Enterprise (MSME) sector in terms of its size, levels of technology employed and range of products and services produced starting from grass root village industries, the products from the sector spans to auto components, microprocessors, electronic components and electro medical devices and highlighted contributes 45% of the manufactured output and 40% of its exports. The highest bracket of loans available to the MSME sector would be up to Rs.10 lakh. For further financing, the MSME sector affiliated entrepreneurs would be given a MUDRA card.

Dr. Kshetrimayum Ranjan Singh (2018), with an objective of focusing on the PMMY schemes and its distinctive features of the initiative taken, current status of the schemes in all the states has published his research article titled “Development of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises through MUDRA Loans with Special Reference to Manipur”. As observed by the author in this study MUDRA scheme helps MSME’s to expand their business operations, many unregistered small businesses got into the bunch of registered sector, Financial positions and profitability of MSMEs were reinforced, MSMEs got a protected against the exploitation of moneylenders, this was the solution for many unemployed youths through offering of MUDRA loan and there by setting up a new business. On the other hand authors also opine that there is a need for transparency and fairness while selecting the beneficiaries of the PMMY from the financial institutions. Author concluded his research study with the opinion that there is a need for fair and effective implementation of this scheme which creates a game changer for the industrially backward region.

Sameer Kochhar (2017) this report explains how to fund the unfunded. According to a survey of NSSO 2013, approximately 5.77 crore small business units in India stabilize MUDRA loans in a big way. Aadhar and mobile details are to be furnished. PMMY has brought about its first major changes by including MFIs and NBFCs within its fold. Through PMMY the number of jobs has substantially increased from 5.44cr to where it stands today. The MUDRA Yojana has had a very positive impact

on the rural economy. The PMMY is a successful financial and social inclusive vehicle backed by technological tools and policies.

Parasuraman Subramani & Sathiya (2017) in an article, emphasized on the role of NBFCs helping economic growth. NBFCs act as intermediary between borrower and lender providing safety and liquidity. NBFCs are not registered under RBI but registered under company act. However, NBFCs provide alternative finance services such as investment, consultant services, brokering money transfer and check cashing. Both banks and NBFCs are major elements of a sound and healthy financial system. Banking is completely relied upon by the country's business households and the public sectors of financial products to reach their financial needs. NBFCs as alternative financial needs with gaining popularity both developed and developing countries. NBFCs provide the demand side of funds as well as facilitate a healthy competition environment in the financial market. The NBFCs help during economic distress in the country. In total NBFC is helping our Indian economy either using the parameter of GDP or Income per capita.

Aparna Rudrawar & Vijay Uttarwar (2016) In this article they have discussed how the MUDRA is channelized under SIDBI as a subsidiary and registered as an NBFC which stands for Non-Banking Financial Corporation, and the role and responsibilities of MUDRAs as the sum of the initiative in promoting the right technology solutions for their last mile, supporting development and promotional activities in the low-income sector. It is a credit delivery to small businesses under the brainchild scheme of Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana. They also discuss after the introduction of the MUDRA Scheme how it has impacted our economy on broader levels i.e., employment creation, women empowerment, creation of capital, improved standards of living contributing to GDP growth. It involves minimal documentation and arm length accessible Credit.

Amiya Kumar Mohapatra (2016) In this article he discusses how finance is an essential blood vein for an entrepreneur, for small business development and the role of micro finance institutions, non-banking financial companies as crucial segments, and the role of formal banking. MUDRA banking is empowered to structure the policy guidelines for micro financing and MUDRA regulates MFIs and NBFCs which are outside the purview of RBI guidelines. MUDRA credit process is quite easy and hassle-free with a proper policy framework. In a successful democratic nation, it should be planned for the unplanned and reach to the unreached sector. Mudra has helped the helpless to get funds at an affordable rate of interest. More contributions are expected in the near future.

Ashish Mahajan (2016) In this article he has studied the performance and impact of MUDRA Yojana. He shows how small businesses play a vital role in a highly populated country like India contributing to the nation's GDP by providing large scale employment. A fast-growing nation cannot ignore the importance of self-sustaining employment while drafting national policies. This article also focuses on ways to resolve hurdles faced by Non –corporates and small business sectors by understanding the MUDRA scheme. The Main objective of MUDRA Scheme is to provide self-employment and to establish small businesses by taking guidelines from aforesaid scheme under Prime Minister Mudra Yojana. Mudra has benefited and will benefit in future urban poor and rural poor and low-income groups with financing aids from Rs 50,000 to Rs. 10, 00,000 depending upon business categories. In future if mudra works properly, it will increase domestic or indigenous products in the markets. It also helps improve the Indian rupee against foreign currency in the international currency markets. Overall Mudra will help create self-employment, women empowerment and improve the conditions of backward sections like uneducated and semi-skilled categories.

Jahangir Ahmad Bhat & Pushpender Yadav (2016) in their paper *'Role of National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD) and Small Industries Development Bank of India (SIDBI) in Indian Microfinance'* have discussed that, many small companies have been benefited by the monetary and persuasive support by NABARD and SIDBI in the sector of microfinance. India, the second-largest nation by population in the world, is developing faster but the surprising fact is that, the world's 1/3rd poor population lives in India. This has resulted in miserable poverty, very low education ratio, very low standard of life, very low sex ratio and heights of exploitation. Microfinance area in the economy is mounting and is suitable for the Indian poor for their wellbeing in all aspects. Without the support of giant institutions like NABARD and SIDBI, Micro finance is incomplete as it offers significant financial resources services to the world in terms of micro-finance and financial institutions. SIDBI is playing a pivotal role in offering bulk finance to MFI/NGOs. In this way they can expand their business operations and reach many entrepreneurs who need finance in small denominations. In the research study, the authors have found that microfinance is a cost-effective instrument for providing financial services to the poor, however, SIDBI is not showing positive growth like NABARD because of various reasons.

Anup Kumar Roy (2016) In his paper MUDRA Yojana – 'A Strategic Tool for Small Business Financing attempted to know about MUDRA Yojana and its Key Objectives and role of MUDRA Bank towards Small Business Units. They discuss constraints of developments of small business.

2.3 Research Gaps

The extensive review of literature in this study has led to the detection of Research Gaps. There were gaps found in the literature with respect to content gaps and methodological gaps. In terms of content, a lot of studies have depicted MUDRA loan studies but have not concentrated on the beneficiaries. The point of view of beneficiaries and impact on them have not been studied

particularly in the literature. In terms of methodology, this study has conducted both qualitative and quantitative analysis and many of the studies have performed only quantitative side of the analysis. Though the data is from the secondary source, it has been directly obtained from the Government's MUDRA loans department from Mumbai and has been the latest data. This is one of the factors that is missing in many research papers. Opinion based analysis and interpretation has been emphasized in many of the studies.

2.4 Summary:

There have been limitless studies conducted on various dimensions of the MSMEs and MUDRA loans in the research sphere and varied literature has been reviewed and presented in this chapter. This enormous literature has been reviewed in detail and the research gaps in this area has been identified and presented in this chapter. The important and relevant literature is mentioned in this chapter.

Chapter 3

RESEARCH DESIGN

3.1 Need of the study

MSMEs play an important role in the economic growth of our country. Funding, being the major challenge for the MSMEs, Government has introduced MUDRA scheme for the needy. This scheme is primarily aimed at MSME units across the country. It was established with the sole purpose of funding and saving small entrepreneurs from abuse by money lenders and helping 1.5 crore new entrepreneurs in developing small businesses. They also provide and generate employment

opportunities. They enhance financial literacy access for the New Technology and Non-Corporate Small Business Sectors (NCSBS) so as not to depend upon money lenders; rather they can approach the financial institutions and bring them under Mudra Borrower Scheme. The scheme also seeks to empower and emancipate women and fund the unfunded new entrepreneur. However, there is a huge lacuna in the system as identified in literature and the initial surveys conducted while writing this proposal. The challenges are in the areas of awareness among the general public, practical processing problems by the banking professionals and identification of actual beneficiaries for the loans. With this background, there is an ardent need to understand the role of MUDRA in entrepreneurship and its impact on Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) beneficiaries. Therefore, the present study attempts to study the same.

3.2 Research Questions

The present study revolves around the following research questions:

1. Is MUDRA scheme really benefiting the stakeholders?
2. Are MSMEs aware of MUDRA schemes and its details?
3. What is the impact of MUDRA schemes on the MSME beneficiaries?
4. Are the youth getting motivated to take up entrepreneurship through MUDRA schemes?

Any other relevant questions that might arise in the course of the study will also be considered.

3.3 Objectives of the Study:

The study has the following major objectives:

1. To evaluate the impact of MUDRA scheme on Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) beneficiaries.
2. To create an impact by documenting the cases.

3.4 Scope of the Study

3.4.1 Conceptual Scope:

The present study is confined to the study of role of MUDRA loans and its impact on the MSME beneficiaries. In order to have an unbiased view, exploratory scope is considered and thereby leading to the study of the actual impact to the beneficiaries.

3.4.2 Geographical Scope:

The present study has considered Karnataka as the geographical scope for two reasons –

According to the regional analysis depicted in MUDRA Annual Report 2019-2020, South region has a clear mention about the performance with regard to Target Vs Achievement on loan sanctions and disbursements. South region has the performance of 29% which is high compared to other regions as mentioned in the below chart.

Fig 3.1: Region-wise Distribution

Source: MUDRA Annual Report-2019-20

Out of top 10 districts rated based on the performance, 50% of the top districts are covered in Southern India. Five districts – Hyderabad, Bangalore Urban, Tiruchirappalli, Belgaum and Chennai are among the top 10 districts as shown in the table below. Hence the present study considers Karnataka as the sample region for data collection.

Fig 3.2: Top 10 districts- District wise performance

District-wise performance

Sr. No.	District Name	FY 2019-20		
		No. of A/Cs	Sanction Amt. (₹ in crore)	Share of the Total Account Sanctioned
1	Hyderabad	11,35,978	4,705	1.82%
2	Bengaluru urban	5,22,505	3,361	0.84%
3	Kolkata	6,76,424	2,831	1.09%
4	Pune	2,51,856	2,348	0.40%
5	North 24 Parganas	5,24,089	2,302	0.84%
6	Ahmedabad	3,96,763	2,276	0.64%
7	Tiruchirappalli	6,16,395	2,264	0.99%
8	Murshidabad	5,79,188	2,065	0.93%
9	Belgaum	3,48,394	2,012	0.56%
10	Chennai	2,56,599	2,001	0.41%
	Total	53,08,191	26,165	8.52%

Source: MUDRA Annual Report-2019-20

3.5 Data collection

As a part of primary data collection, various questionnaires and survey instruments were designed as applicable to collect relevant data from various stakeholders. The secondary data includes information from online journals, books, reports and other documents pertaining to the study. Most importantly, MUDRA loans data was collected directly from the Government of India Directorate on MUDRA loans through email mode.

Qualitative data was also collected from the direct beneficiaries of MUDRA loan and case study methodology has been applied to study and analyse the qualitative data. An initial attempt was made at the time of proposal writing to understand the nuances of MUDRA loans which included understanding the needs of the customers, banking professionals' view on MUDRA loan sanctions and disbursements and another view of the youth who are either existing entrepreneurs or potential entrepreneurs.

3.5.1: Preliminary Survey Results

As a part of a background work to arrive at the objectives and research questions, a small qualitative survey was conducted among 30 respondents. The respondents were conveniently selected based on the study's requirement.

Fig 3.3: Respondents of the Preliminary Survey

Source: Original Preliminary Survey by the author (2021)

Three separate open ended survey forms were used to collect qualitative data and were analysed.

- The first set of respondents were the existing Entrepreneurs in small businesses. They were posed a question about their views on MUDRA scheme and many of them were of the opinion that more entrepreneurs should be educated about this scheme and the

Government should reach public at large. A few of them also felt that this scheme has made them self-dependent and in turn boosts the economy of the country.

- The second set of respondents were from the Banking Institutions whose Banking service experiences ranged between 5 to 31 years. Out of these respondents, few of them were of the opinion that the Government should stop all subsidy related scheme and give the interest incentive so that the public money reaches the actual beneficiaries. Many of them felt that the process should be made simpler for sanctions and disbursements. Few of them have perceived that identification of beneficiaries is a biggest challenge for the banks.
- The third set of respondents who were the youth were of the opinion that many of them were not aware of such a scheme which is existing in the Banks and is introduced by Government of India. Few youths were of the view that, assessment of the business proposals and strict vigilance of their business is necessary in order to make sure the money is utilised in an appropriate way. Many youths have also urged that government should encourage aspiring young entrepreneurs by helping them with less paper work and faster approval of loans.

Apart from the above excerpts, many suggestions and ideas were also presented by the respondents during the online discussion of the topic. Based on these thoughts, the objectives and the research study mapping has been designed.

3.6 Summary:

This chapter covers the need for the study, the Research Questions, Objectives of the study, the conceptual scope and geographical scope of the study, Data Collection methods and the statistical techniques used for the study. It covers all the research tools, techniques and processes used in this research.

Chapter-4

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

4.1 Introduction

The present study is aimed at analysis of the data from both the qualitative and quantitative ends. Relevant analytical tools will be used in the course of the research. A Model will be developed after validation by the experts and the users. The user manual/handbook will be designed for the MUDRA loan aspirants and will be tested and evaluated.

Table 4.1 : Total Number of Accounts of Shishu for 5 years

**Total No. of accounts of SHISHU for 5 years i.e., 2016-17 to 2020-21
in different Banks/Financial Institutions**

Years	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21
Total - SBI and Associates	8,60,165 (2.36)	7,98,577 (1.87)	21,14,366 (4.10)	30,72,304 (5.64)	7,43,069 (1.85)
Total - Public Sector Commercial Banks	19,34,990 (5.30)	17,10,815 (4.01)	20,83,695 (4.05)	25,46,364 (4.67)	44,05,279 (10.96)
Total - Private Sector Commercial Banks	84,20,195 (23.07)	94,02,971 (22.04)	1,12,34,138 (21.81)	1,87,80,712 (34.47)	1,57,65,390 (39.24)
State Cooperative Banks	NA	NA	197 (0.00)	58 (0.00)	20 (0.00)
Total - Regional Rural Banks	9,26,498 (2.54)	8,08,234 (1.89)	7,65,050 (1.49)	7,21,610 (1.32)	7,19,020 (1.79)
Total - Micro Finance Institutions	11,29,709 (3.10)	18,00,974 (4.22)	18,79,391 (3.65)	20,59,118 (3.78)	9,10,055 (2.26)

Years	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21
Total - NBFC-Micro Finance Institutions	2,01,82,496 (55.30)	2,00,33,628 (46.95)	2,25,55,542 (43.79)	1,68,32,312 (30.89)	1,20,06,911 (29.88)
Total - Non-Banking Financial Companies	1,95,293 (0.54)	62,64,310 (14.68)	44,63,729 (8.67)	46,28,174 (8.49)	19,33,926 (4.81)
Total – Small Finance Banks	28,48,467 (7.80)	18,50,286 (4.34)	64,11,330 (12.45)	58,49,965 (10.74)	36,96,445 (9.20)
Grand Total	3,64,97,813 (100.00)	4,26,69,795 (100.00)	5,15,07,438 (100.00)	5,44,90,617 (100.00)	4,01,80,115 (100.00)

(Figures in parenthesis show percentage to total)

Table 4.1 shows the details of total number of accounts of SHISHU for 5 years i.e., 2016-17 to 2020-21. It can be observed that the number of accounts in case of NFBC-Micro Finance Institutions, which had contributed a maximum of 2,01,82,496 (55.3%) during 2016-17 had reduced to 1,20,06,911 (29.88%) during 2020-21 and the number of accounts in case of Total - Public Sector Commercial Banks had shown an increase from 19,34,990 (5.30 %) during 2016-17 to 44,05,279 (10.96%) during 2020-21 along with Total - Private Sector Commercial Banks which increased from 84,20,195 (23.07%) during 2016-17 to 1,57,65,390 (39.24%) during 2020-21.

It can be observed that there was a shift of number of accounts from financial institutions to banks in case of SHISHU Accounts.

Fig 4.1- Total Number of Shishu Accounts

Index

1	Total - SBI and Associates	5	Total - Micro Finance Institutions
2	Total - Public Sector Commercial Banks	6	Total - NBFC-Micro Finance Institutions
3	Total - Private Sector Commercial Banks	7	Total - Non-Banking Financial Companies
4	Total - Regional Rural Banks	8	Total - Small Finance Banks

Fig 4.1 shows the bar diagram of the total number of SHISHU accounts confirming the information given in the Table 1.

Table 4.2 Total Number of Kishore Accounts

**Total No. of accounts of KISHORE for 5 years i.e., 2016-17 to 2020-21
in different Banks/Financial Institutions**

Years	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21
Total - SBI and Associates	3,41,199 (12.81)	4,09,067 (8.79)	4,05,922 (6.14)	3,98,373 (6.16)	4,41,204 (4.65)
Total - Public Sector Commercial Banks	12,86,539 (48.30)	17,10,782 (36.76)	14,97,350 (22.67)	14,10,345 (21.79)	18,15,988 (19.14)
Total - Private Sector Commercial Banks	3,00,449 (11.28)	9,27,510 (19.93)	19,01,603 (28.79)	19,06,701 (29.46)	40,96,658 (43.19)
Total - Foreign Banks	88 (0.00)	137 (0.00)	272 (0.00)	85 (0.00)	0 (0.00)
State Cooperative Banks	NA	NA	60 (0.00)	64 (0.00)	30 (0.00)
Total - Regional Rural Banks	4,99,471 (18.75)	6,52,279 (14.02)	7,11,424 (10.77)	7,60,788 (11.76)	8,39,605 (8.85)
Total - Micro Finance Institutions	0 (0.00)	7,896 (0.17)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	42,368 (0.45)
Total - NBFC-Micro Finance Institutions	1,07,984 (4.05)	63,976 (1.37)	2,94,164 (4.45)	7,28,425 (11.26)	10,72,841 (11.31)
Total - Non-Banking Financial Companies	1,13,558 (4.26)	7,48,419 (16.08)	11,92,476 (18.05)	2,75,201 (4.25)	5,05,788 (5.33)
Total - Small Finance Banks	14,214 (0.53)	1,33,858 (2.88)	6,02,736 (9.12)	9,91,891 (15.33)	6,71,678 (7.08)
Grand Total	26,63,502 (100.00)	46,53,874 (100.00)	66,06,009 (100.00)	64,71,873 (100.00)	94,86,160 (100.00)

(Figures in parenthesis show percentage to total.)

Table 4.2 shows the details of total number of accounts of KISHORE for 5 years i.e., 2016-17 to 2020-21. It can be observed that the number of accounts in case of Total - Public Sector Commercial Banks, which had contributed a maximum of 12,86,539 (48.30%) during 2016-17 had reduced to 18,15,988 (19.14%) during 2020-21 and the number of accounts in case of Total - Private Sector Commercial Banks had shown an increase from 3,00,449 (11.28%) during 2016-17 to 40,96,658 (43.19%) during 2020-21.

It can be observed that the Banks, over all, had a greater number of accounts compared to financial institutions in case of KISHORE Accounts though the number of accounts was showing an increase in case of financial institutions. The number of accounts held by Total - Foreign Banks and State Cooperative Banks was negligible during the five-year period.

Fig 4.2 Total Number of Kishore Accounts

Index

1	Total - SBI and Associates	5	Total - NBFC-Micro Finance Institutions
2	Total - Public Sector Commercial Banks	6	Total - Non-Banking Financial Companies
3	Total - Private Sector Commercial Banks	7	Total - Small Finance Banks
4	Total - Regional Rural Banks		

Fig 4.2 shows the bar diagram of the total number of KISHORE accounts confirming the information given in the Table 3.2.

Table 4.3 Total Number of Tarun Accounts

**Total No. of accounts of TARUN for 5 years i.e., 2016-17 to 2020-21
in different Banks/Financial Institutions**

Years	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21
Total - SBI and Associates	1,54,442 (28.61)	2,02,361 (25.08)	2,16,791 (12.34)	2,05,540 (15.99)	3,01,303 (28.19)
Total - Public Sector Commercial Banks	2,34,802 (43.50)	3,02,072 (37.44)	3,46,145 (19.70)	3,48,242 (27.10)	3,53,752 (33.10)
Total - Private Sector Commercial Banks	1,00,820 (18.68)	1,25,993 (15.61)	1,42,248 (8.10)	1,79,337 (13.95)	1,75,174 (16.39)
Total - Foreign Banks	145 (0.03)	158 (0.02)	297 (0.02)	47 (0.00)	0 (0.00)
State Cooperative Banks	NA	NA	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)
Total - Regional Rural Banks	20,364 (3.77)	27,696 (3.43)	31,620 (1.80)	40,348 (3.14)	43,612 (4.08)
Total - Micro Finance Institutions	0	0	0	0	0

Years	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21
	(0.00)	(0.00)	(0.00)	(0.00)	(0.00)
Total - NBFC-Micro Finance Institutions	1,278 (0.24)	443 (0.05)	1,14,289 (6.51)	1,726 (0.13)	719 (0.07)
Total - Non-Banking Financial Companies	27,839 (5.16)	1,15,462 (14.31)	1,97,485 (11.24)	1,91,330 (14.89)	1,72,343 (16.13)
Total - Small Finance Banks	42 (0.01)	32,739 (4.06)	7,07,996 (40.30)	3,18,546 (24.79)	21,868 (2.05)
Grand Total	5,39,732 (100.00)	8,06,924 (100.00)	17,56,871 (100.00)	12,85,116 (100.00)	10,68,771 (100.00)

(Figures in parenthesis show percentage to total)

Table 4.3 shows the details of total number of accounts of TARUN for 5 years i.e., 2016-17 to 2020-21. It can be observed that the number of accounts in case of Total - Public Sector Commercial Banks, which had contributed a maximum of 2,34,802 (43.50%) during 2016-17 had reduced to a low of 3,46,145 (19.70%) during 2018-19 and increased to 3,53,752 (33.10%) during 2020-21 and the number of accounts in case of Total - SBI and Associates had also shown a reduction from 1,54,442 (28.61%) during 2016-17 to 2,16,791 (12.34%) during 2018-19 and reached a high of 3,01,303 (28.19%) during 2020-21.

It can be observed that the Banks, over all, had a greater number of accounts compared to financial institutions in case of TARUN Accounts though the number of accounts was showing an increase in case of financial institutions except Micro Finance Institutions, whose contribution was nil. The number of accounts held by Total - Foreign Banks and State Cooperative Banks were negligible during the five-year period.

Fig 4.3 Number of Tarun Accounts

Index

1	Total - SBI and Associates	5	Total - NBFC-Micro Finance Institutions
2	Total - Public Sector Commercial Banks	6	Total - Non-Banking Financial Companies
3	Total - Private Sector Commercial Banks	7	Total - Small Finance Banks
4	Total - Regional Rural Banks		

Fig 4.3 shows the bar diagram of the total number of TARUN accounts confirming the information given in the Table 4.3. Data regarding number of accounts and Sanctioned / Disbursed loans at SBI and Associates, Public Sector Commercial Banks, Private Sector Commercial Banks, Regional Rural Banks and Small Finance Banks were grouped and titled as Banks and Micro Finance Institutions, NBFC, which means, Micro-Finance Institutions and Non-Banking Financial Companies were grouped and titled as Financial Institutions (FIs) to facilitate further analysis.

Table 4.4 shows Total No. of Accounts for 5 years i.e., 2016-17 to 2020-21 in different Banks/Financial Institutions which were grouped and the figures in parenthesis show the percentage of contribution by Bank/FIs to that particular type of loan.

Table 4.4 – Total number of accounts

Total No. of Accounts for 5 years i.e., 2016-17 to 2020-21 in different Banks/Financial Institutions								
Year	SHISHU		KISHORE		TARUN		TOTAL	
	Banks	FIs	Banks	FIs	Banks	FIs	Banks	FIs
2016-17	1,49,90,315 (41)	2,15,07,498 (59)	24,41,872 (92)	2,21,542 (8)	5,10,470 (95)	29,117 (5)	1,79,42,657 (45)	2,17,58,157 (55)
2017-18	1,45,70,883 (34)	2,80,98,912 (66)	38,33,496 (82)	8,20,291 (18)	6,90,861 (86)	1,15,905 (14)	2,35,09,264 (49)	2,46,21,034 (51)
2018-19	2,26,08,776 (44)	2,88,98,662 (56)	51,19,097 (77)	14,86,640 (23)	14,44,800 (82)	3,11,774 (18)	2,91,72,673 (49)	3,06,97,076 (51)
2019-20	3,09,71,013 (57)	2,35,19,604 (43)	54,68,162 (84)	10,03,626 (16)	10,92,013 (85)	1,93,056 (15)	3,75,31,188 (60)	2,47,16,286 (40)
2020-21	2,53,29,223 (63)	1,48,50,892 (37)	78,65,163 (83)	16,20,997 (17)	8,95,709 (84)	1,73,062 (16)	2,75,15,733 (62)	1,66,44,951 (38)

(Figures in parenthesis show percentage to that particular loan type)

As shown in Table 4.4, Banks accounted for 1,49,90,315 (41%) number of Shishu accounts during 2016-17 which increased to 2,53,29,223 (63%) during 2020-21 whereas FIs accounted for 2,15,07,498 (59%) number of Shishu accounts during 2016-17 which reduced to 1,48,50,892 (37%) during 2020-21. In case of Kishore accounts, Banks accounted for 24,41,872 (92%) during 2016-17 which reduced to 78,65,163 (83%) during 2020-21 whereas FIs accounted for 2,21,542 (8%) during 2016-17 which increased to 16,20,997 (17%) during 2020-21. Tarun accounts also had shown the similar trend like Kishore accounts wherein Banks accounted for 5,10,470 (95 %) during 2016-17

which reduced to 8,95,709 (84%) during 2020-21 whereas FIs accounted for 29,117 (5%) during 2016-17 which increased to 1,73,062 (16%) during 2020-21. The aggregate contribution in terms of number of accounts in total increased in case of Banks from 1,79,42,657 (45%) during 2016-17 to 2,75,15,733 (62%) during 2020-21 where as it had shown a reduction from 2,17,58,157 (55%) during 2016-17 to 1,66,44,951 (38%) in case of FIs.

It can be concluded that the Banks in general had accounted for a greater number of accounts in all the three types of loans than FIs.

Fig 4.4 depicts the Table 4.4 as a percentage to each type of loan accounts individually and in total.

Fig 4.4 Total Number of Accounts

The Fig 4.4 clearly depicts that the contribution of banks in terms of number of accounts as a percentage to each loan type and total is much higher in recent years compared to earlier years let it be any type of loan or in totality.

Table 4.5 shows the amount and percentage of loans sanctioned and disbursed by banks and financial institutions during the five years i.e., 2016-17 to 2020-21

Table 4.5 Amount and percentage of loans sanctioned and disbursed by banks and financial institutions, individually, during the five years i.e., 2016-17 to 2020-21.

Amount in Rs. Crores											
Year		2016-17		2017-18		2018-19		2019-20		2020-21	
		Banks	FIs	Banks	FIs	Banks	FIs	Banks	FIs	Banks	FIs
Shishu	S	40,277	44,824	43,011	62,991	67,971	74,374	93,404	70,155	63,380	46,574
	D	39,739	44,152	42,521	61,707	67,279	72,372	92,761	70,053	62,278	46,359
	%	47	53	41	59	48	52	57	43	58	42
Kishore	S	49,588	3,954	71,935	14,793	81,354	23,024	82,652	12,923	1,11,704	20,812
	D	47,111	3,949	68,455	14,738	76,927	22,932	78,617	12,807	1,06,546	20,793
	%	93	7	83	17	78	22	86	14	84	16
Tarun	S	39,855	2,016	53,286	7,644	61,759	13,209	62,947	15,407	68,091	11,199
	D	38,338	2,007	51,355	7,644	59,236	13,033	60,356	15,115	64,787	11,091
	%	95	5	87	13	82	18	80	20	86	14
Total	S	1,29,720	50,794	1,68,231	85,428	2,11,084	1,10,608	2,39,004	98,485	1,70,616	78,585
	D	1,25,189	50,108	1,62,331	84,089	2,03,443	1,08,338	2,31,734	97,974	1,68,444	78,243
	%	72	28	66	34	66	34	71	29	68	32

(S = Sanctioned, D = Disbursed), (% = percentage of loan sanctioned/disbursed during the year)

Note: The difference between Loans sanctioned and disbursed in terms of percentage was negligible.

As shown in Table 4.5, Banks accounted for 47% of Shishu loans sanctioned /disbursed which increased to 58% during 2020-21 compared to financial institutions which accounted for 53% during 2016-17 which reduced down to 42% during 2020-21. In case of Kishore loans, Banks accounted for

a high of 93% during 2016-17 which marginally reduced to 84% during 2020-21 whereas financial institutions contributed to 7% during 2016-17 which increased to 16% during 2020-21. Tarun loans also had shown the similar trend like Kishore loans wherein Banks accounted for 72 % during 2016-17 which reduced to 68% during 2020-21 whereas financial institutions accounted for 5% during 2016-17 which increased to 14% during 2020-21. In total, 72% of loans were sanctioned/disbursed by banks during 2016-17 which reduced to 68% during 2020-21 where as in case of financial institutions it increased from 28% during 2016-17 to 32% during 2020-21.

Graph 4.5, 4.6, 4.7 and 4.8 shows the year wise disbursement of loans as a percentage by Banks and Financial Institutions.

Fig 4.5 Year wise distribution of Shishu Loans as a percentage

Fig 4.6 Year wise distribution of Kishore Loans as a percentage

Fig 4.7– Year wise distribution of Tarun Loans as a percentage

Fig 4.8 – Year wise distribution of Total Loans as a percentage

As can be observed, more percentage of Shishu loans were sanctioned /disbursed by financial institutions compared to banks.

Table 4.6 showing Different Loan amounts sanctioned/disbursed during the 5 years i.e. 2016-17 to 2020-21 and their percentage.

Table 4.6 Different loan amounts sanctioned/disbursed

**Different Loan amounts sanctioned/disbursed during the 5 years
i.e. 2016-17 to 2020-21 and their percentages to Total**

amount in Rs. Crores

Year		2016-17		2017-18		2018-19		2019-20		2020-21	
		Banks	FIs								
Shishu	S	40,277	44,824	43,011	62,991	67,971	74,374	93,404	70,155	63,380	46,574
	D	39,739	44,152	42,521	61,707	67,279	72,372	92,761	70,053	62,278	46,359

Year		2016-17		2017-18		2018-19		2019-20		2020-21	
		Banks	FIs	Banks	FIs	Banks	FIs	Banks	FIs	Banks	FIs
	%	31	88	26	74	32	67	39	71	26	59
Kishore	S	49,588	3,954	71,935	14,793	81,354	23,024	82,652	12,923	1,11,704	20,812
	D	47,111	3,949	68,455	14,738	76,927	22,932	78,617	12,807	1,06,546	20,793
	%	38	8	43	17	39	21	35	13	46	26
Tarun	S	39,855	2,016	53,286	7,644	61,759	13,209	62,947	15,407	68,091	11,199
	D	38,338	2,007	51,355	7,644	59,236	13,033	60,356	15,115	64,787	11,091
	%	31	4	32	9	29	12	26	16	28	14
Total	S	1,29,720	50,794	1,68,231	85,428	2,11,084	1,10,608	2,39,004	98,485	2,43,175	78,585
	D	1,25,189	50,108	1,62,331	84,089	2,03,443	1,08,338	2,31,734	97,974	2,33,511	78,243
	%	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

(S=Sanctioned, D=Disbursed, %=percentage of loan sanctioned/disbursed to total during the year)

Note: The difference between Loans sanctioned and disbursed in terms of percentage was negligible.

As shown in Table 4.6 Banks accounted for 31% of Shishu loans sanctioned/disbursed which remained more or less the same during the 5 years compared to financial institutions which accounted for 88%, highest among the loans, during 2016-17 which reduced down to 59% during 2020-21. In case of Kishore loans, Banks accounted for 38% during 2016-17 which marginally increased to 46% during 2020-21 whereas financial institutions contributed to 8% during 2016-17 which increased to 26% during 2020-21. Tarun loans also had shown the similar trend like Kishore loans wherein Banks accounted for 31 % during 2016-17 which reduced to 28% during 2020-21 whereas FIs accounted for 4%) during 2016-17 which increased to 14% during 2020-21.

Table 4.7 shows the loans sanctioned/disbursed by banks as a percentage to total.

Loans Sanctioned / Disbursed by Banks as a percentage to Total

Year	Shishu	Kishore	Tarun	Total
2016-17	31	38	31	100
2017-18	25	43	32	100
2018-19	32	39	29	100
2019-20	39	35	26	100
2020-21	26	46	28	100

Single Factor ANOVA was used to test whether there is significant difference between Shishu, Kishore or Tarun loans (as a percentage of totals) sanctioned /disbursed by banks with the

Hypothesis:

H₀; There is no significant difference between Shishu, Kishore or Tarun loans (as a percentage of total) sanctioned/disbursed by banks.

H₁; There is significant difference between Shishu, Kishore or Tarun loans (as a percentage of total) sanctioned/disbursed by banks.

Table 4.8 The hypothesis was tested using Single Factor Anova, the results were as shown as:

Anova: Single Factor						
SUMMARY						
<i>Groups</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>		
Shishu	5	153.9605	30.7921	30.10433		
Kishore	5	200.0455	40.00911	19.36876		
Tarun	5	145.9939	29.19879	4.519722		
ANOVA						
<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
Between Groups	340.5914	2	170.2957	9.462132	0.003414	3.885294
Within Groups	215.9712	12	17.9976			
Total	556.5626	14				

As shown in ANOVA Table, the p value is less than 0.05 or F calculated value (9.46) is higher than table value (3.885) the Null Hypothesis is rejected. It indicates that there is significant difference between different types of loans sanctioned/disbursed by banks.

Table 4.9 shows Loan Sanctioned/Disbursed by Financial Institutions as a percentage of Total.

Loans sanctioned / Disbursed by Financial Institutions as a percentage of Total			
Year	Shishu	Kishore	Tarun
2016-17	88	8	4
2017-18	74	17	9
2018-19	67	21	12
2019-20	71	13	16
2020-21	59	26	14

Single Factor ANOVA was used to test whether there is significant difference between Shishu, Kishore or Tarun loans (as a percentage of total) sanctioned /disbursed by financial institutions with the Hypothesis:

Hypothesis:

H₀; There is no significant difference between Shishu, Kishore or Tarun loans (as a percentage of total) sanctioned/disbursed by financial institutions.

H₁; There is significant difference between Shishu, Kishore or Tarun loans (as a percentage of total) sanctioned/disbursed by financial institutions.

4.10 The hypothesis was tested using Single Factor Anova, the results were as shown as:

Anova : Single Factor						
SUMMARY						
<i>Groups</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>		
Shishu	5	359.7229	71.94458	113.0933		
Kishore	5	85.52235	17.10447	51.13019		
Tarun	5	54.75473	10.95095	21.666		
ANOVA						
<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
Between Groups	11275.88	2	5637.94	90.9886	5.61E-08	3.885294
Within Groups	743.5578	12	61.96315			
Total	12019.44	14				

As shown in ANOVA Table, the p value is less than 0.05 or F calculated value (90.98) is higher than table value (3.885) the Null Hypothesis is rejected. It indicates that there is significant difference between different types of loans sanctioned/disbursed by financial institutions.

Table 4.11 shows the Shishu loans sanctioned/disbursed by Banks and Financial Institutions during the five years, i.e., 2016-17 to 2020-21

Shishu		
Year	Banks	FIs
2016-17	31	88
2017-18	26	74
2018-19	32	67
2019-20	39	71
2020-21	26	59

Student's t-test was used to test whether there is significant difference between Shishu loans (as a percentage of total) sanctioned/disbursed by banks and financial institutions with the Hypothesis:

H₀; There is no significant difference between Shishu loans (as a percentage of total) sanctioned / disbursed by banks and financial institutions.

H₁; There is significant difference between Shishu loans (as a percentage of total) sanctioned/disbursed by banks and financial institutions.

4.12 The hypothesis was tested using Student's t-test, the results were as shown as:

t-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means		
	<i>Banks</i>	<i>FIs</i>
Mean	30.792103	71.9445833
Variance	30.10433	113.093253
Observations	5	5
Pearson Correlation	0.1810857	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	4	
t Stat	-8.328848	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.0005677	
t Critical one-tail	2.1318468	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.0011355	
t Critical two-tail	2.7764451	

It can be observed from the table that there was low positive correlation (0.18) between Shishu loans sanctioned/disbursed by Banks and Financial Institutions. The p value was less than 0.05 and the calculated value of t (8.329) was higher than the table value (2.132), the Null Hypothesis is rejected. It indicates that there is significant difference between Shishu loans (as a percentage of total) sanctioned/disbursed by banks and financial institutions.

Table 4.13 shows the Kishore loans sanctioned/disbursed by Banks and Financial Institutions during the five years, i.e., 2016-17 to 2020-21.

Kishore		
Year	Banks	FIs
2016-17	38	8
2017-18	43	17
2018-19	39	21
2019-20	35	13
2020-21	46	26

Student's t-test was used to test whether there is significant difference between Kishore loans (as a percentage of total) sanctioned/disbursed by banks and financial institutions with the Hypothesis:

H₀; There is no significant difference between Kishore loans (as a percentage of total) sanctioned/disbursed by banks and financial institutions.

H₁; There is significant difference between Kishore loans (as a percentage of total) sanctioned/disbursed by banks and financial institutions.

Table 4.14 The hypothesis was tested using Student's t-test, the results were as shown as:

t-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means		
	<i>Banks</i>	<i>FIs</i>
Mean	40.009107	17.1044695
Variance	19.368758	51.1301927
Observations	5	5
Pearson Correlation	0.7065794	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	4	
t Stat	10.039026	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.0002768	
t Critical one-tail	2.1318468	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.0005536	
t Critical two-tail	2.7764451	

It can be observed from the table that there was high positive correlation (0.71) between Kishore loans sanctioned/disbursed by Banks and Financial Institutions. The p value was less than 0.05 and the calculated value of t (10.03) was higher than the table value (2.132), the Null Hypothesis is rejected. It indicates that there is significant difference between Kishore loans (as a percentage of total) sanctioned/disbursed by banks and financial institutions.

Table 4.15 shows the Tarun loans sanctioned/disbursed by Banks and Financial Institutions during the five years, i.e., 2016-17 to 2020-21.

Tarun		
Year	Banks	FIs
2016-17	31	4
2017-18	32	9
2018-19	29	12
2019-20	26	16
2020-21	28	14

Student's t-test was used to test whether there is significant difference between Tarun loans (as a percentage of total) sanctioned/disbursed by banks and financial institutions with the Hypothesis:

H₀; There is no significant difference between Tarun loans (as a percentage of total) sanctioned/disbursed by banks and financial institutions.

H₁; There is significant difference between Tarun loans (as a percentage of total) sanctioned/disbursed by banks and financial institutions.

Table 4.16 The hypothesis was tested using Student’s t-test, the results were as shown as:

t-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means		
	<i>Banks</i>	<i>FIs</i>
Mean	29.198787	10.9509451
Variance	4.5197225	21.6660005
Observations	5	5
Pearson Correlation	-0.831929	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	4	
t Stat	6.2478894	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.0016728	
t Critical one-tail	2.1318468	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.0033455	
t Critical two-tail	2.7764451	

It can be observed from the table that there was high negative correlation (-0.83) between Tarun loans sanctioned/disbursed by Banks and Financial Institutions. The p value was less than 0.05 and the calculated value of t (6.25) was higher than the table value (2.132), the Null Hypothesis is rejected. It indicates that there is significant difference between Tarun loans (as a percentage of total) sanctioned/disbursed by banks and financial institutions.

Therefore, it can be concluded that over all Banks are contributing to a greater number of accounts and sanctioning / disbursement of loans compared to Financial Institutions.

4.2 Qualitative Analysis:

As a part of the qualitative analysis exercise, entrepreneurs who have availed MUDRA loans were interviewed and the responses were analysed. The following word cloud was created out of the responses and the paragraphs that follow the cloud has the details of the qualitative factors arrived out of the analysis.

Fig 4.9 Word Cloud representing qualitative data

It is evident from the above word cloud that the cases which were interviewed, had the following positive opinion on MUDRA loans:

4.2.1 No Collateral Security: Since MUDRA loans do not expect any collateral security to be provided against the loans, it is easy to secure. Entrepreneurs were happy with this arrangement and felt relieved that not all the businessmen do not have collateral security to present.

4.2.2 More Employment: MUDRA loans have created employment to many people. When the businesses are expanded, entrepreneurs tend to hire employees to manage their businesses. The loan gives them to support to hire people.

- 4.2.3 Easy Business Expansion:** Business expansion is easy when MUDRA loan is availed. The entrepreneurs are stress-free and can easily expand their business.
- 4.2.4 Increases Confidence:** MUDRA loans provide easy access to loans and the businessmen in this case study is of the opinion that it increases their confidence while conducting businesses.
- 4.2.5 Increased Self-Employment:** A lot of people get strength and support to start businesses and become self-employed instead of waiting for getting employment elsewhere. It encourages the youth to take up self-employed businesses.
- 4.2.6 Financial Improvement:** Due to MUDRA loans, the financial stability of the business will be improved. It boosts the financial status of the entrepreneurs to a considerable extent.

Table 4.17 List of case details collected through Interview method:

Sl. No.	Questions	Case No.1	Case No. 2	Case No.3	Case No.4	Case No.5	Case No.6
1	Name	Mr. Sanjay	Mr. M Suman	Mr. Shankarappa B	Mr. Raju	Mr. Ashwath Narayan	Mr. Vimal H
2	Age	42	36	39	30	75	40
3	Nature of Business	Car Workshop	Digital marketing	Books and stationery	Old paper Mart	Rice Mill	Textile
4	Registered Address of Business	# 224, 6A cross, Gokulnagar, Karesandra, K R Road, B S K 2nd Stage, Bangalore - 560076	Prosocial Marketing solutions Pvt Ltd, # 46, Novel tech park, Hosur Road, Bangalore	S L V Enterprises,# 125, Sri Rangatha nilaya, Kempegowda Nagar, Magadi Road, Bengaluru 560091	No.89, Nageshwara Rao Garden, Durgamma Temple Street, Kalasipalya, Bengaluru 560002	NR Extension, Chintamani	Jayanagar, Bangalore
5	Number of Owners	1	2	1	1	1	1
6	Number of employees	8	5	1	2	25	2
7	Nature of funding from business	Private fund + Mudra Loan	Pvt equity, Mudra Loan	Mudra loan	Private Mudra Loan	Private funds	Private Equity

Sl. No.	Questions	Case No.1	Case No. 2	Case No.3	Case No.4	Case No.5	Case No.6
8	Amount of Mudra loan borrowed	6,00,000	5,00,000	1,50,000	5,00,000	0	0
9	Year in which loan is availed	2020	2020	2021	2014	NA	NA
10	Have you done any repayment of the loan in terms of interest or principal?	Yes (Interest)	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA	NA
11	Number of years active in the present business	15	3 years	1 year 5 months	5 years	50	20
12	Problems faced by you currently	Right now, no issues	Competition	Yes, we need lot of experience to get a loan		Online Availability of similar products	Online business and competition
13	Have you seen any improvement in the business after availing mudra loan? If yes, what kind of improvement?	Yes, after availing mudra loan expansion of business was done easily. Able to hire more workers	Yes, as there is no collateral security, funds are not blocked	Yes financial. a little improvement in business	Yes	No	No

Sl. No.	Questions	Case No.1	Case No. 2	Case No.3	Case No.4	Case No.5	Case No.6
14	Do you Think Mudra loan has led to Employment Generation through you in your business?	Mudra Loan have created opportunities for small business/self-employment. By providing loan to entrepreneur increases the confidence in themselves and also creates employment opportunities for others also	Yes, it has helped	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
15	Do you think Mudra loan scheme has helped you to expand your Business?	Definitely it has helped me to expand business	Definitely	Yes, it is. But so many people are not repaying the loans. I need additional loan for expansion	Yes	Nil	No
16	Any other comments you would like to make on Mudra Loans scheme? (Personal opinion of the beneficiary)	Hope the facilities provided by the Mudra loan scheme continue for long time.	No CIBIL score required so it is very helpful and is helping small scale business	It is good but repayment problem is bad. For young businessmen and start-up people it is good.	No	No	No

4.3 Summary:

This chapter covers the quantitative and qualitative analysis of the study. This research has adopted case study methodology under the qualitative analysis and the cases has been presented in detail. Under the quantitative analysis various descriptive analysis presentations have been made in the form of tables and graphs. Hypotheses has also been presented in this chapter and the results are interpreted in detail.

Chapter 5

SUGGESTIONS, SOCIAL IMPACT OF RESEARCH AND CONCLUSION

5.1 Introduction

The researcher has drawn Suggestions and Conclusion from quantitative and qualitative (a case study) analysis to give suggestions to Banks/ other Financial Institutions, to Youth and to beneficiaries.

5.2 Suggestions to the Banks/Other Financial Institutions

- The Banks/Other Financial Institutions should make sure NPAs are reduced by making sure they recover loans from the MUDRA borrowers.
- The Banks/Other Financial Institutions should give equal importance to all types of MUDRA loans, viz., Shishu, Tarun and Kishore schemes.
- The NPAs are more under Shishu Scheme as the amount of loan is very meagre. Hence, Banks/Other Financial Institutions should concentrate on this and make sure the loans are recovered
- The Banks/Other Financial Institutions should create a dedicated cell for MUDRA scheme so that general public gets enough information about the scheme and reaches the public at large.

5.3 Suggestions to the Youth

India has a demographic dividend with the highest youth population and it is time now for us to initiate new startups with innovation and creativity. Hence, the following suggestions:

- The youth of India should think from the entrepreneurial perspective rather than the employment perspectives
- The Government of India Schemes should be read and understood by the youth.
- The Youth of India should understand self-employment is better than being employed and should take pride in creating employment by being self-employed.
- The youth should try to get the benefit themselves from the Government schemes or they have to at least educate the needy in the relevant areas.
- The Youth should volunteer in the nation building by advertising mudra schemes among the small and informal business sector like street vendors, small shops etc. in their neighborhood.

5.4 Suggestions to the Beneficiaries/Prospective loan borrowers:

- The Beneficiaries are of the opinion that Government schemes are a cumbersome process. This is a myth and the beneficiaries should reach out to the Banks and try to get more information
- The Beneficiaries should visit the Government website to understand the loan options and schemes based on their requirement and capacities.
- The Beneficiaries should be ethical in repaying the loan and should not neglect the repayment aspect as the Government has provided the option of “No Collateral security” as a benefit to the small businessmen not as an avoidance of repayment.

- The Beneficiaries should try to employ people in their business, however small the salaries/wages could be, thereby creating employment and contributing to the country's economy.

5.5 Social Impact of Research

The Impact of this research reaches beyond academia, though academia will also be benefited out of the results of this research. The teaching fraternity should go beyond the set boundaries and teach the students of management about entrepreneurship which is the best alternative for employment. Students at the young age should be made aware that their innovative ideas will not go waste due to lack of finance availability. Even though, they cannot get the finances to the extent they expect, the Government at present through their initiatives and JanSamarth portal is trying to assist and handhold new ideas. The dissemination of this work will also generate significant impact and will help the bankers to use it as a reference.

5.6 Conclusion

The Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana (PMMY) has been continuously serving millions of unfunded micro-borrowers in our country with finances that are crucial for their businesses and enterprise activities which has resulted in upliftment of their life styles. The PMMY programme, since its announcement, in the last five years, has benefited 24.48 crore loan accounts, with a loan sanction of whopping 18.6 trillion rupees, since the year 2015. This has enabled the grassroots of the economy of the country and contribute in a bigger way to the overall economic growth. The proposed study is about to contribute extensively to MSME stakeholders and academicians. Researchers in this area should also consider disseminating these kinds of cases to the general public and the academic arena and make sure it reaches many people and help them get greater benefits through various Government initiatives. The rural public

should also be created awareness about the schemes and help them to grow through the MUDRA loan set up.

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APPENDIX I

SURVEY FORM FOR ENTREPRENEURS (BENEFICIARIES)

1. Name:
2. Age:
3. Nature of Business:
4. Number of owners:
5. Number of Employees:
6. Nature of funding from Business:
7. Number of years active in the present business:
8. Are you aware of the Government's Mudra Loan Scheme?
Yes: No:
If the answer to Question Number 8 is Yes, have you availed it?
Yes: No:
If the answer to question number 9 is yes, is it easy to avail it in Banks?
Yes: No:
If the answer to Question number 10 is Yes, what are your experiences on the Mudra Loan Scheme?
9. Please share any other views you may have on getting the help from the Government in financing small businesses like yours.

Institute Of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India
Dr. Mahesh K.M., Post-Doctoral Research Scholar,-21SUPDR008

INSTITUTE OF MANAGEMENT & COMMERCE

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

MANGALORE, KARNATAKA, INDIA

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A List of

**Publications, Extracts of Published Papers,
Certificates of IPR Generated & Plagiarism Report**

**Submitted to the College of Management and Commerce, Srinivas
University in partial fulfillment of the requirements for POST-
DOCTORAL RESEARCH FELLOW PROGRAM in the Area of
MUDRA LOAN & ITS IMPACT ON MICRO, SMALL AND MEDIUM
ENTERPRISES OF KARNATAKA**

Dr. Mahesh K.M., Post-Doctoral Research Scholar,-21SUPDR008

APPENDIX II
PUBLICATION FROM THE REPORT

Institute Of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India
Dr. Mahesh K.M., Post-Doctoral Research Scholar,-21SUPDR008

Refereed Journal Articles:

1. Mahesh K. M. , P. S. Aithal & Sharma K. R. S.(2021) A Study on the Impact of Schemes and Programmes of Government of India on Agriculture to Increase Productivity, Profitability, Financial Inclusion, and Welfare of Farmers to Transform them into Modern Society. International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS), ISSN: 2581-6012, Vol. 6, No. 2, December 2021. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5765895>
2. Mahesh K. M., P. S. Aithal & Sharma K. R. S.(2022) Impact of Sustainable Finance on MSMEs and other Companies to Promote Green Growth and Sustainable Development. International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML), ISSN: 2581-7000, Vol. 6, No. 1, February 2022. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6044523>
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Impact Factor : 5.7631(UIF)

Institute Of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India
Dr. Mahesh K.M., Post-Doctoral Research Scholar,-21SUPDR008

APPENDIX III

BOOK CHAPTERS

1. Mahesh K. M., P. S. Aithal & Sharma K. R. S (2022).UGC Sponsored Two Day National Seminar
“Impact of Information Technology on Healthcare: Issues and Challenges. Published by Dept. of

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Institute Of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India
Dr. Mahesh K.M., Post-Doctoral Research Scholar,-21SUPDR008

APPENDIX IV

CERTIFICATE OF IPR GENERATED

Institute Of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India
Dr. Mahesh K.M., Post-Doctoral Research Scholar,-21SUPDR008

APPENDIX V

PLAGIARISM REPORT

Institute Of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India
Dr. Mahesh K.M., Post-Doctoral Research Scholar,-21SUPDR008

SSRN PAPERS REPORT

Institute Of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India
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MUDRA LOAN & ITS IMPACT ON MICRO, SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES BENEFICIARIES IN KARNATAKA

**A Report Submitted in Partial Fulfilment of the Requirements for Award
of **POST DOCTORAL FELLOW****

Dr. MAHESH K M
Roll No: 21SUPDR008

Under the supervision of
Dr. P. S. Aithal

**INSTITUTE OF MANAGEMENT & COMMERCE
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE, KARNATAKA, INDIA**

July 2022

MUDRA loan and its impact on Micro, Small and Medium Enterprise Beneficiaries in Karnataka

SYNOPSIS

Submitted by

Dr MAHESH K M

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

for the Post-Doctoral fellow Programme

2022

APPENDIX I

SURVEY FORM FOR ENTREPRENEURS (BENEFICIARIES)

1. Name:
2. Age:
3. Nature of Business:
4. Number of owners:
5. Number of Employees:
6. Nature of funding from Business:
7. Number of years active in the present business:
8. Are you aware of the Government's Mudra Loan Scheme? Yes: No:
If the answer to Question Number 8 is Yes, have you availed it?
Yes: No:
If the answer to question number 9 is yes, is it easy to avail it in Banks?
Yes: No:
If the answer to Question number 10 is Yes, what are your experiences on the Mudra Loan Scheme?
9. Please share any other views you may have on getting the help from the Government in financing small businesses like yours.

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UNIVERSITY

MANGALORE, KARNATAKA, INDIA

July 2022

A List of

**Publications, Extracts of Published Papers,
Certificates of IPR Generated & Plagiarism Report**

Submitted to the College of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University in partial fulfillment of the requirements for POST-DOCTORAL RESEARCH FELLOW PROGRAM in the Area of MUDRA LOAN & ITS IMPACT ON MICRO, SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES OF KARNATAKA

Dr. Mahesh K.M., Post-Doctoral Research Scholar,-21SUPDR008

APPENDIX II

PUBLICATION FROM THE REPORT

5. Mahesh K. M., P. S. Aithal & Sharma K. R. S (2022) Role of MUDRA in Promoting SMEs/MSE, MSMEs, and allied Agriculture Sector in the rural and urban area - To Achieve 5 Trillion Economy. International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS), ISSN: 2581-6012, Vol. 7, No. 1 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6556154>,
6. Mahesh K. M., P. S. Aithal & Sharma K. R. S (2022).IMPACT OF NEP 2020- TRANSFORMATION OF EDUCATION ECOSYSTEM. Review of Research. ISSN: 2249- 894X Impact Factor : 5.7631(UIF)

APPENDIX III BOOK

CHAPTERS

1. Mahesh K. M., P. S. Aithal & Sharma K. R. S (2022).UGC Sponsored Two Day National Seminar “Impact of Information Technology on Healthcare: Issues and Challenges. Published by Dept. of Commerce and Business Administration, ANU Ongole Campus, Ongole. India. ISBN:978-93-5593-528-1
2. Mahesh K. M., P. S. Aithal & Sharma K. R. S (2022) Volume-2.FinTech,AI,ML,Startup Transformed Financial Services and Financial Inclusion of SMEs/MSMEs in India to Achieve Sustainable Economic Growth. Research Article. 1-56.MSMEs.ACS PUBLISHER, Delhi, India. ISBN: 978-93-94893-02-3
3. Mahesh K. M.& P. S. Aithal (2022) Government Schemes & Policy, SMEs and MSMEs 4.0 Industry: The Catalyst for Indian Gig Economy. Reverberations in Indian Economy Post COVID-19. Volume-1. Lekhit Publications, Kerala.ISBN: 978-81-954429-1-1

APPENDIX IV

CERTIFICATE OF IPR GENERATED

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